

Palladium(II) Chelates of α -Oximinoacetoacetarylamide Thiosemicarbazones

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IN continuation of our previous work¹⁻⁷, we describe the preparation and characterisation of Pd(II) chelates of α -oximinoacetoacetarylamide thiosemicarbazones in the present paper.

Experimental*Preparation of the Pd(II) chelates of the α -oximinoacetoacetanilide thiosemicarbazone :*

10 ml aqueous solution of Pd(II) chloride (0.05M) was gradually added to 25 ml alcoholic solution (2%) of α -oximinoacetoacetanilide thiosemicarbazone and acidified with dilute HCl. The mixture was diluted to about 100 ml with distilled water and digested on waterbath for half an hour. The red precipitates separated were filtered, washed with hot water and aqueous ethanol (1:1), and dried in an oven at 110°. The Pd(II) chelates of the other α -oximinoacetoacetarylamide thiosemicarbazones of the series were prepared in the similar manner. The m. p., colour, elemental analysis and composition of the Pd(II) chelates are given in Table. The infrared spectra of the ligands and chelates were recorded in KBr pellets.

Results and Discussion*Infrared spectra :*

An assignment of the important infrared absorption bands is based on the study of infrared spectra

of the free ligands and their chelates. The band at 2833-2890 cm^{-1} appears in the ligands but does not appear in the chelates. This indicates the presence of intramolecular H-bond in the ligands⁸. The absence of this band in the chelates is the indication of the replacement of hydrogen of oximino group by metal ion. The fact that νNO shifts from 952-966 cm^{-1} in the free ligands to 1160-1180 cm^{-1} in the chelates indicates that the coordination of the ligand to the metal is through N and not through O of oximino group and the chelates contain the nitron (N \rightarrow O) type of linkage which is known to absorb at about 1200 cm^{-1} as a very strong band⁹. The shift of νNO from about 1000 cm^{-1} in ligand to about 1200 cm^{-1} shows the nitronic type of linkage in many oxime complexes¹⁰⁻¹². The lowering of the $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching frequency from 1600-1610 cm^{-1} in the ligands to 1590-1595 cm^{-1} in the chelates is indicative of 1-N coordination of thiosemicarbazide moiety. The $\nu\text{N-N}$ band around 1030-1045 cm^{-1} in the ligands shifts to the higher frequency in the chelates. The magnitude of this positive shift (15-30 cm^{-1}) indicates the monodentate linkage of N-N residue¹³. The presence of C=S bands at 826-840 cm^{-1} and 1050-1083 cm^{-1} in the free ligands as well as in chelates suggest that C=S group is not involved in the coordination of metal¹⁴. Further more it indicates that the ligands act as bidentate and not as tridentate. The infrared spectra of the ligands and chelates reveal bands around 3300, 3100 and 3460 cm^{-1} , indicating secondary association, primary association and free N-H vibrations of amides respectively¹⁵. The strong bands in the ligands and chelates around 1620 and 1660 cm^{-1} , 1540 cm^{-1} and 1300 cm^{-1} are attributed to amide I, II and III bands respectively¹⁵.

From infrared spectra and metal : ligand ratio (1:2) of the chelates, it is concluded that α -oximinoacetoacetarylamide thiosemicarbazones act as bidentate ligands.

TABLE—PALLADIUM CHELATES OF α -OXIMINOACETOACETARYLAMIDE THIOSEMICARBAZONES

No.	R	Composition	Colour	m.p. °C (decomp.)	% Palladium		% Nitrogen	
					Found	Requd.	Found	Requd.
1.	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₁₀ O ₄ S ₂ Pd	Red	178	16.16	16.10	21.0	21.12
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₁₀ O ₄ S ₂ Pd	Orange red	208	15.32	15.45	20.18	20.27
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₁₀ O ₄ S ₂ Pd	Deep red	200	15.39	15.45	20.20	20.27
4.	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂ Pd	Deep red	360	14.52	14.58	19.09	19.14
5.	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂ Pd	Orange	207	14.55	14.58	19.20	19.14
6.	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂ Pd	Red	210	14.50	14.58	19.10	19.14
7.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₁₀ O ₆ S ₂ Pd	Red	195	14.69	14.77	19.28	19.37
8.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₁₀ O ₆ S ₂ Pd	Red	222	14.80	14.77	19.27	19.37
9.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₁₀ O ₄ S ₂ Pd	Deep red	286	14.78	14.84	19.42	19.48
10.	2,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₁₀ O ₈ S ₂ Pd	Orange	232	13.70	13.63	17.78	17.89
11.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₁₀ O ₆ S ₂ Pd	Orange red	215	14.17	14.21	18.78	18.65

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Physical Properties of Iron Lauryl Sulphate and Laurate Solutions in 1-butanol

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A number of workers¹⁻⁵ have reported a considerable information about the physical properties of soaps in 1-butanol. In this note a comparative study of these properties of iron lauryl sulphate and laurate has been carried out.

Experimental

The chemicals were purified and the compounds prepared by the method reported earlier⁸. Excess of solid compounds and 1-butanol were equilibrated at different temperatures by thorough stirring. The thermostat bath was controlled to within $\pm 0.5^\circ$. Clear supernatant saturated solution was taken only when the equilibrium was attained (after 1-2 hrs) with pipette, evaporated, dried and weighed. The apparatus and procedure of conductivity and viscosity measurements were the same as described elsewhere^{6,7}.

Results and Discussion

Solubility: Solubility of compounds (Table 1) increases with increase in temperature. It is observed that the solubility of lauryl sulphate increases very slowly with increase in temperature. This behaviour is also found for laurate at low temperatures but an abrupt increase in solubility occurs at higher temperatures. The low solubility is due to its molecular state and formation of micelles in solutions increases the solubility abruptly.

The plots of $\log S$ vs $1/T$ are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a point corresponding to Krafft point i.e., 45° and 50° for lauryl sulphate and laurate respectively. The apparent heat of solution, ΔH_{sol} has been calculated by the following relationship

$$\Delta H_{sol} = RT^2 \left[\frac{d \ln S}{dT} \right] \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where S is the solubility in moles litre⁻¹ and other terms have their usual significances. The values of ΔH_{sol} below and above Krafft point are 11.44, 0.71 and 2.29, 0.17 Kcals mole⁻¹ respectively for laurate and lauryl sulphate.

Conductivity: Specific conductivity, k of solutions increases with increasing concentration at different temperatures. The plots (Fig. 1) of k vs C are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite concentration (Table 1) indicating CMC for laurate. However, the plots of lauryl sulphate are non-linear with concentration below CMC. The CMC value of lauryl sulphate solution increases with rise in temperature whereas the value for laurate is independent of temperature.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF SOLUBILITY, CMC AND CONSTANTS A AND B OF IRON COMPOUNDS IN 1-BUTANOL AT TEMPERATURES (35-50°)

Temp. in °C	Lauryl sulphate				Laurate			
	Solubility (g/100 g)	CMC (moles litre ⁻¹)	A	B	Solubility (g/100 g)	CMC (moles litre ⁻¹)	A	B
35	2.90	0.006	1.71	0.48	1.41	0.008	1.46	0.26
40	2.92	0.007	1.78	0.45	1.55	0.008	1.40	0.29
45	3.05	0.008	1.86	0.43	2.51	0.008	1.64	0.23
50	3.08	0.010	1.92	0.41	3.39	0.008	1.36	0.30
55	3.10				3.65			
60	3.13				3.86			